

Microbial Population Structure in the Rhizosphere of Maize (*Zea mays* L), and Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench] at Various Stages of Plant Development.

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Abstract

This study investigated microbial population structure in the rhizosphere of maize and okra at different stages of plant development. The study was conducted at faculty of Agriculture Teaching and Research Farm, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Seeds of maize and okra were purchased and planted, soil samples were collected and analyzed before planting and at different stages of plant development, bacterial and fungal count and isolation, and extraction of plant parasitic nematodes were done using standard methods. Data generated was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the mean difference was separated using least significant difference at 5%. Results showed highest occurrence as follows: *Bacillus spp* (54%) in the rhizosphere of maize and okra during seedling and maturity stages respectively, *Staphylococcus spp* (38%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage, *Streptococcus spp* (18%) in the rhizosphere of okra during flowering stage, *Lactobacillus* (12%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage; *Rhizopus spp* (63%) in the rhizosphere of okra during flowering stage, *Aspergillus spp* (41%) in the rhizosphere of maize during seedling stage, *Yeast spp* (15%) in the rhizosphere of maize during seedling stage, *Fusarium spp* (30%) in the rhizosphere of okra during maturity stage, and *Mucor spp* occurrence (7%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage; *Meloidogyne spp* (17%) in the rhizosphere of okra during flowering stage, *Pratylenchus spp* (41%) in the rhizosphere of maize during seedling stage, *Helicotylenchus spp* (67%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage, and *Tylenchus spp* (33%) in the rhizosphere of maize during maturity stage. The study concluded that there were variations in microbial communities in response to plant growth and development.

Keywords: Population Structure, Rhizosphere, Maize, Okra, Seedling Stage, Fruiting Stage

INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most important crops in the world (Hou *et al.*, 2020), it is a major source of food, animal feed, and fuel and is grown in many nations worldwide (Chebotar *et al.*, 2023). Maize yield is affected by applied hybrid and fertilization, and the rhizosphere of maize has been reported to harbor an array of microorganisms (Bojtor *et al.*, 2021; Mousavi *et al.*, 2021).

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* [L.] Moench) is a common annual vegetable crop that is grown in tropical and subtropical regions worldwide (Meena *et al.*, 2017). The fibrous fruits or pods that contain spherical white seeds are highly prized due to their frequent use in soups, salads, and as a spice when dried and ground into powder (Roslan *et al.*, 2022). Also, because of its high vitamin, mineral, and antioxidant content, okra has been rated as a very nutritious vegetable, and it is commonly grown in economically disadvantaged areas of Asia and Africa and can promote food security during periods of environmental change (Perveen *et al.*, 2023). In addition to vitamins, minerals, and plant proteins, fresh okra fruit is a good source of dietary fibre, and the mucilage of okra, which has a protein and edible oil content of around 20%, is used as medication (Agregán *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, minerals including pyridoxine, folates, calcium, iron, and phosphorus, as well as vitamins C, B6, and K, support the maintenance of physiological bodily functions (Petropoulos *et al.*, 2018). Abiotic stressors, environmental factors, infections, and nutrient losses all significantly reduce okra output (Saima *et al.*, 2022). Poor okra growth and yield are made worse by low soil fertility or an improper fertilization approach (Roslan *et al.*, 2022). For the top 10 okra-producing nations, such as Cameroon, Nigeria, and Iraq, which are considered low yielders (<6 t/ha) in comparison to India (12.3 t/ha), this is especially concerning (Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], 2022).

The nutrient-rich, extremely malleable soil layer that envelops the plant root is called the rhizosphere, and a rich and varied fauna, including microorganisms (microbiomes), can be found in this microzone (Roslan *et al.*, 2022). According to Singh and Godwin (2022), plant microbiomes are made up of a variety of microorganisms that can be friendly, neutral, or harmful, such as bacteria, fungi, oomycetes, algae, protozoa, nematodes, and viruses; these

beneficial microbial communities support the growth, health, and productivity of plants (Brader *et al.*, 2017; Lemanceau *et al.*, 2017). For example, root endophytic bacteria encourage maize development in cold environments (Beirinckx *et al.*, 2020), while the root bacterial population improves the growth and health of *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants cultivated in greenhouses (Duran *et al.*, 2018). Also, by altering the expression of defense genes, the endophyte *Metarhizium robertsii* suppresses insect proliferation and promotes plant growth, hence maintaining a favorable connection with maize (Niu *et al.*, 2017; Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). The microbiome is greatly impacted by abiotic factors, including soil pH, soil type, root exudates, soluble dissolved organic matter, temperature, UV radiation, moisture, field location, plant age, pathogens, agricultural methods, and plant genetics (Correa-Galeote *et al.*, 2018; Singh and Godwin, 2022). All of the aforementioned factors have the potential to alter plant microbiome, which could affect plant productivity and health (Singh and Godwin, 2022).

Given the aforementioned findings, our aim was to investigate microbial population structure in the rhizosphere of maize and okra at different stages of plant development. This is to add to existing literature, and provide more basis for the use of maize and okra as intercrops to increase soil microbial biomass which aids in organic matter decomposition, thereby improving soil fertility.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted at faculty of Agriculture Teaching and Research Farm, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria between May and September 2024. Port Harcourt is found in the subequatorial region of Nigeria. Port Harcourt lies between latitude 4°07' and 5°50'N and longitude 6°05'04' and 7°3'20'E on an elevation of 18m above sea level. The mean annual rainfall ranges from about 3000-4500mm (FAO, 1984) with a bimodal pattern, starting in March and ending in November with peaks in June and September and short period of dry spell in August usually known as August break (Eludoyin *et al.*, 2015).

Experimental Layout

An experimental area of 20m x 20m was used to carry out the study. The experimental area was manually cleared and the layout was marked using tape, pegs, and ropes. Beds of 4m x 4m were raised on each of the plot with a 1m alley way. Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with five (5) replications was also adopted.

Source of Planting Materials and Planting

The seeds of maize, and okra, were purchased from Aluu community local market, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Maize and okra seeds were planted directly on the Field at a depth of 0.5m.

Soil Sampling

Soil samples were collected using a soil auger at a depth of 0-20cm before planting. Rhizosphere soil samples were collected from two plant stands in each plot, by carefully uprooting and shaking the soil adhering to the roots into a labeled polybag at each growth stages. The collected soil samples from the two plant stands per plot were bulked into a composite sample for microbial analysis and physiochemical analysis. Samples were collected from each treatment with 3 replicates. A total of 12 samples were collected at each sampling interval. They were placed into well labeled poly bags and then transferred to laboratory for analysis. Cylindrical metal cores of 6cm were used to obtain undisturbed soil samples for physical analysis.

Sample Collection for Nematode

The roots and soil at the rhizosphere were randomly collected from two plants per plot and were bulked into a composite sample; this was repeated at the three (3) selected growth stages (seedling, flowering, and maturity).

Soil samples were collected from two plant stands in each plot using at a depth of 0-20cm with a hand trowel in the rhizosphere of each plant at the different growth stages. The collected soil samples from the two plant stands per plot were bulked into a composite sample. The samples were properly labeled in polythene bags with the crop type, replicate and the growth stage at which the sample was collected. A total of 25 soil samples were collected at each growth stage.

Roots of each crop were collected from the same plant stand from which the soils samples were collected. The roots of the plants were removed using knife after the soil had been removed to expose the roots. The roots were also bulked

into composite samples and were properly labeled in polythene bags as the soil samples, so as to prevent moisture loss and desiccation of roots prior to laboratory analysis.

Bacteria count and isolation

Bacteria communities in soils were determined using viable plate count for counting colony from bacterial and propagules. The bacteria count and isolation was determined using the serial dilution and spread plate techniques in nutrient agar as described by Fawole *et al.*, (2001). The samples were inoculated for 24 hours, and biochemical tests were carried out for identification of isolates.

Fungal count and isolation

Fungal count was determined using the spread plate method on potato dextrose agar (PDA) as described by Monica (2001). Soil samples were prepared by 10 fold serial dilution with 1 gram of soil sample. The samples were inoculated for 4 days and the isolated colonies were counted, identified using lacto-phenol and direct microscopic view as described by Monica (2001).

Extraction of Plant Parasitic Nematodes from Soil Samples

Plant parasitic nematodes were extracted from soil samples using extraction tray method as described by Coyne *et al.*, (2007). Each of the composite samples was mixed and 250ml of soil was measured using a 250ml beaker and was poured into lined plastic sieve with facial tissue which was placed on well labeled plastic flat plate. 200ml of water was poured into the side of the plastic sieve to gradually wet the soil. The set-up was left undisturbed in the laboratory for 48hours, after which the sieve was carefully lifted from the plastic plate while the nematode suspension in the plate was poured into well labeled small disposable cup, the plate was rinsed into the suspension in the cup and was allowed to settle. The nematode suspension was decanted and the supernatant was poured into a labeled 30ml vials and kept in the refrigerator at 4°C prior to identification and counting of nematode species.

Extraction of Plant Parasitic Nematodes from Root Samples

Plant parasitic nematodes were extracted from root samples using extraction tray method as described by Coyne *et al.*, (2007). Each of the composite samples was rinsed with distilled water in to remove soil particles. The roots were finely chopped into small pieces of 1-2cm with a sharp knife. 10g was weighed using a sensitive balance and was poured into lined plastic sieve with facial tissue which was placed on well labeled plastic flat plate. 200ml of water was poured into the side of the plastic sieve to gradually wet the root. The set-up was left undisturbed in the laboratory for 48hours, after which the sieve was carefully lifted from the plastic plate while the nematode suspension in the plate was poured into well labeled small disposable cup, the plate was rinsed into the suspension in the cup and was allowed to settle. The nematode suspension was decanted and the supernatant was poured into a labeled 30ml vials and kept in the refrigerator at 4°C prior to identification and counting of nematode species.

Nematode Identification and Counting

Aliquot of 2ml nematode suspension was pipette into a Doncaster counting dish as described by Doncaster (1962). The Doncaster counting dish was placed under a dissecting microscope and compound microscope alternately for identification and counting of plant parasitic nematodes using Bell's Key (Bell, 2004). The mean number of nematodes calculated from the suspension was multiplied by the total volume of the suspension to get the total number of plant parasitic nematodes in each sample.

Statistical Analysis

Data generated was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the mean difference was separated using least significant difference at 5%. Analytical software used was Genstart Discovery 3rd edition, 2009.

RESULT

Soil Microbial Count and Population Structure before Planting

The result for soil microbial counts and soil microbial population structure before planting is shown in Table 1. Nematode count was the same (600) in both maize and okra plots, bacteria count was higher in maize plot (100) compared with okra plot (85), while fungi count was higher in okra plot (8) compared with maize plot (4). Bacteria species include: *Staphylococcus spp*, *Bacillus spp*, *streptococcus spp*, Fungi species include: *Aspergillus spp*, *Rhizopus*, *Yeast*, while nematode species include: *Pratylenchus spp*.

Table 1: Soil Microbial Count and Population Structure before Planting

Microbial Count	Maize Plot	Okra Plot	Microbial Species
Bacteria (x10 ³ Cfu/g of soil)	100	85	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i> , <i>Bacillus spp</i> , <i>streptococcus spp</i>
Fungi (x10 ³ Cfu/g of soil)	4	8	<i>Aspergillus spp</i> , <i>Rhizopus</i> , <i>Yeast</i> .
Nematode	600	600	<i>Pratylenchus spp</i> .

Soil Microbial Population Structure at Seedling Stage

The result of microbial population structure at seedling stage is shown in Table 2. Bacteria species were the same in the rhizosphere of maize and okra and include: *Staphylococcus spp*, *streptococcus spp*, and *Bacillus spp*. For fungi species, *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, and *Yeast* were isolated in the rhizosphere of maize while *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, and *Fusarium* were isolated in the rhizosphere of okra. For nematode, *Helicotylenchus spp* was isolated in the rhizosphere of okra while *Helicotylenchus spp*, and *Pratylenchus spp* were isolated in the rhizosphere of okra.

Table 2: Soil Microbial Population Structure at Seedling Stage

Crops	Seedling Stage		
	Bacteria Isolates	Fungi Isolates	Nematode Isolates
Maize	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i> , <i>streptococcus spp</i> , <i>Bacillus spp</i> .	<i>Aspergillus</i> , <i>Rhizopus</i> , <i>Yeast</i> .	<i>Helicotylenchus spp</i> .
Okra	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i> , <i>streptococcus spp</i> , <i>Bacillus spp</i> .	<i>Aspergillus</i> , <i>Rhizopus</i> , <i>Fusarium</i> .	<i>Helicotylenchus spp</i> , <i>Pratylenchus spp</i> .

Soil Microbial Population Structure at Flowering Stage

The result of soil microbial population structure at flowering stage is shown in Table 3.

Bacteria species in the rhizosphere of maize include: *Staphylococcus spp*, *streptococcus spp*, *Lactobacillus*, and *Bacillus spp*, while those in the rhizosphere of okra include: *Staphylococcus spp*, *streptococcus spp*, *Corynebacterium*, and *Bacillus spp*. For fungi species, *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, and *Yeast* were isolated in the rhizosphere of maize while *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, and *Mucor* were isolated in the rhizosphere of okra. For nematode, *Helicotylenchus spp* and *Pratylenchus spp* were isolated in the rhizosphere of okra while *Meloidogyne spp*, *Helicotylenchus spp*, and *Pratylenchus spp* were isolated in the rhizosphere of okra.

Table 3: Soil Microbial Population Structure at Flowering Stage

Crops	Bacteria Isolates	Fungi Isolates	Nematode Isolates
Maize	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i> , <i>streptococcus spp</i> , <i>Lactobacillus</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> <i>spp</i> .	<i>Aspergillus</i> , <i>Rhizopus</i> , <i>Yeast</i> .	<i>Helicotylenchus spp</i> , <i>Pratylenchus spp</i> .
Okra	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i> , <i>streptococcus spp</i> , <i>Corynebacterium</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> <i>spp</i> .	<i>Aspergillus</i> , <i>Rhizopus</i> , <i>Mucor</i> .	<i>Meloidogyne spp</i> , <i>Helicotylenchus spp</i> , <i>Pratylenchus spp</i> .

Soil Microbial Population Structure at Maturity Stage

The result of soil microbial population structure at maturity stage is shown in Table 4. Bacteria species in the rhizosphere of maize include: *Staphylococcus spp*, *streptococcus spp*, and *Bacillus spp*, while those in the rhizosphere of okra include: *Staphylococcus spp*, *streptococcus spp*, and *Pseudomonas*. For fungi species, *Aspergillus*, and *Rhizopus* were isolated in the rhizosphere of maize while *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, and *Fusarium* were isolated in the rhizosphere of okra. For nematode, *Tylenchus spp* was isolated in the rhizosphere of okra while *Tylenchus spp*, *Helicotylenchus spp*, *Pratylenchus spp* were isolated in the rhizosphere of okra.

Table 4: Soil Microbial Population Structure at Maturity Stage

Crops	Bacteria Isolates	Fungi Isolates	Nematode Isolates
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Maize	<i>Staphylococcus spp,</i> <i>streptococcus spp,</i> <i>Bacillus spp.</i>	<i>Aspergillus, Rhizopus.</i>	<i>Tylenchus spp.</i>
Okra	<i>Staphylococcus spp,</i> <i>streptococcus spp,</i> <i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>	<i>Aspergillus, Rhizopus,</i> <i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Tylenchus spp,</i> <i>Helicotylenchus spp,</i> <i>Pratylenchus spp.</i>

Percentage Occurrence of Bacteria Species at Different Stages of Growth

The result of percentage occurrence of bacteria species at different stages of growth is shown in Table 5. *Bacillus spp* occurrence was highest (54%) in the rhizosphere of maize and okra during seedling and maturity stages respectively, *Staphylococcus spp* occurrence was highest (38%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage, *Streptococcus spp* occurrence was highest (18%) in the rhizosphere of okra during flowering stage, *Lactobacillus* was highest (12%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage, among others.

Table 5: Percentage Occurrence of Bacteria Species at Different Stages of Growth

Crops	Seedling Stage						
	<i>Bacillus spp</i>	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i>	<i>Streptococcus spp</i>	<i>Lactobacillus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas spp</i>	<i>Cyanobacterium</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Maize	54	32	13	0	0	0	0
Okra	50	36	14	0	0	0	0
Crops	Flowering Stage						
	<i>Bacillus spp</i>	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i>	<i>Streptococcus spp</i>	<i>Lactobacillus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas spp</i>	<i>Cyanobacterium</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Maize	27	38	22	12	0	0	0
Okra	47	28	18	4	0	2	0
Crops	Maturity Stage						
	<i>Bacillus spp</i>	<i>Staphylococcus spp</i>	<i>Streptococcus spp</i>	<i>Lactobacillus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas spp</i>	<i>Cyanobacterium</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Maize	52	18	15	0	0	0	0
Okra	54	35	13	0	5.7	0	0

Percentage Occurrence of Fungi Species at Different Stages of Growth

The result of percentage occurrence of fungi species at different stages of growth is shown in Table 6. *Rhizopus spp* occurrence was highest (63%) in the rhizosphere of okra during flowering stage, *Aspergillus spp* occurrence was highest (41%) in the rhizosphere of maize during seedling stage, *Yeast spp* occurrence was highest (15%) in the rhizosphere of maize during seedling stage, *Fusarium spp* occurrence was highest (30%) in the rhizosphere of okra during maturity stage, and *Mucor spp* occurrence was highest (7%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage.

Table 6: Percentage Occurrence of Fungi Species at Different Stages of Growth

Crops	Seedling Stage				
	<i>Rhizopus spp</i>	<i>Aspergillus spp</i>	<i>Yeast spp</i>	<i>Fusarium spp</i>	<i>Mucor spp</i>
Maize	44	41	15	0	0
Okra	53	39	0	8	0
Crops	Flowering Stage				
	<i>Rhizopus spp</i>	<i>Aspergillus spp</i>	<i>Yeast spp</i>	<i>Fusarium spp</i>	<i>Mucor spp</i>
Maize	49	38	5	0	7
Okro	63	31	0	0	6
Crops	Maturity Stage				
	<i>Rhizopus spp</i>	<i>Aspergillus spp</i>	<i>Yeast spp</i>	<i>Fusarium spp</i>	<i>Mucor spp</i>
Maize	55	37	6	0	0
Okro	41	29	0	30	0

Percentage Occurrence of Nematode Species at Different Stages of Growth

The result of percentage occurrence of nematode species at different stages of growth is shown in Table 7. *Meloidogyne spp* occurrence was highest (17%) in the rhizosphere of okra during flowering stage, *Pratylenchus spp* occurrence was highest (41%) in the rhizosphere of maize during seedling stage, *Helicotylenchus spp* occurrence was highest (67%) in the rhizosphere of maize during flowering stage, and *Tylenchus spp* occurrence was highest (33%) in the rhizosphere of maize during maturity stage.

Table 7: Percentage Occurrence of Nematode Species at Different Stages of Growth

Crops	Seedling Stage			
	<i>Meloidogyne spp</i>	<i>Pratylenchus spp</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus spp</i>	<i>Tylenchus spp</i>
Maize	0	0	33	0
Okra	0	50	50	0

Flowering Stage				
Maize	0	33	67	0
Okra	17	33	50	0
Maturity Stage				
Maize	0	0	0	33
Okra	0	50	25	25

DISCUSSION

Soil microorganisms despite making up less than 0.5% (w/w) of the soil mass, are essential to its characteristics and functions (Yan *et al.*, 2015). By converting organic debris into plant nutrients, they play a crucial part in soils. Nonetheless, a number of biotic and abiotic variables influence the microbial characteristics, community structure, and functions of soil microorganisms (Szoboszlai *et al.*, 2019; Kumar *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2021).

In this study, before planting, three bacterial species (*Staphylococcus spp*, *Bacillus spp*, *streptococcus spp*) were isolated from the soil in the study area (Table 1), these species were also isolated during seedling stage (Table 2), and at the flowering stage, *Lactobacillus*, and *Corynebacterium* were isolated from the rhizosphere of maize and okra respectively increasing the number of bacterial isolates to five (Table 3). At the maturity stage, *Lactobacillus*, and *Corynebacterium* were absent but *Pseudomonas spp* was isolated in the rhizosphere of okra in addition to the bacterial isolates recorded during the seedling stage thereby bringing the total number of bacterial isolates to four (Table 4). These bacterial species are among the 20 species that were isolated in the rhizosphere and rhizoplane of okra in the study by Pandey *et al.* (2020). The current results concur with those of Nidhi *et al.* (2016) and Pandey *et al.* (2018), who observed a comparatively similar bacterial diversity and physical traits in the wheat rhizosphere. More or less comparable rhizobacteria have been found in the rhizosphere and rhizoplane of *Brassica oleracea* by Fazal Mahmood *et al.* (2018). In agreement with these findings, Navarro-Noya *et al.* (2022) reported that the degree to which the maize rhizosphere impacted the soil bacterial community varied according to the community trait and the stage of development of the maize plant. Arguably, the increase in the species of bacteria during flowering could be due to fact that the rhizosphere began to enrich specific bacteria and functions related to cofactors and vitamin synthesis during flowering, but functions related to biosynthesis decreased. This position is supported by Navarro-Noya *et al.* (2022) who posited that the bacterial community structure, taxonomic diversity, and functional diversity of the soil bacteria in the maize rhizosphere were different during maize development, and bacterial functions favored in the rhizosphere during plant growth showed that at the early stages of maize development root exudates stimulated bacterial growth. Also, a number of studies have documented that the composition of the bacterial community in the rhizosphere varies throughout plant development, suggesting that roots choose for distinct microorganisms at different times, most likely due to variations in the composition of the root-exudates (Qiao *et al.*, 2017; Yin *et al.*, 2017; Wattenburger *et al.*, 2019).

Furthermore, in this study, fungi and nematode species isolated before planting are *Aspergillus spp*, *Rhizopus*, *Yeast*, and *Pratylenchus spp* (Table 1), during seedling stage, *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, *Yeast*, *Fusarium*, *Helicotylenchus spp*, and *Pratylenchus spp* were isolated (Table 2), during flowering stage, *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, *Yeast*, *Mucor*, *Meloidogyne spp*, *Helicotylenchus spp*, and *Pratylenchus spp* were isolated (Table 3), and during maturity stage, *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus*, *Fusarium*, *Tylenchus spp*, *Helicotylenchus spp*, and *Pratylenchus spp* were isolated (Table 4). At various phases of maize and okra growth, notable variations in fungal and nematode populations were observed. These variations in terms of richness, diversity, and relative abundances of taxa and metabolic processes have been reported in studies by Vital-Lopez *et al.* (2016), Szoboszlai *et al.* (2019), and Singh and Godwin (2022). Curiously, in addition to variations due to growth phases, other research have demonstrated variations in bacterial and fungal communities among cultivars, transgenic and non-transgenic lines, and soil types (van Wyk *et al.*, 2017). As opined by Singh and Godwin (2022), the rhizosphere of maize had a stronger effect on bacterial communities than on fungal communities due to the ecological and environmental filtering action of the root.

Furthermore, the rhizobiome community structure in the carbon-rich area surrounding the plant root differs between plant species and genotypes (Semchenko *et al.*, 2021), because of the influence of the plant, including differences in root exudate patterns (Lopez-Guerrero *et al.*, 2022). Differential generation of root exudates and community utilization are the basis for the host genotype-dependent variation in the root exudate profile and the ensuing substrate-driven or bottom-up changes in the microbial community structure (Yadav *et al.*, 2023). Maize and Okra rhizosphere microbiome has been found to be shaped in part by soil characteristics as pH, nitrogen and potassium availability, phosphate fertilization, and root exudates (Tao *et al.*, 2017; Emmett *et al.*, 2020). These factors might have contributed to the variations in microbial population structure in this study. Furthermore, the composition of maize endophytes was impacted by the combined application of heavy metals and chelants in the soil, indicating their potential to

enhance maize's phytoremediation ability (Islam *et al.*, 2016; Vigliotta *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Wu *et al.*, 2017; Panitlertumpai *et al.*, 2018; Sun *et al.*, 2018).

The kind of soil and the stage of development of maize growth and okra had have a substantial impact on the rhizosphere microbiome and percentage occurrence of microorganisms also showed significant variations in this study (Tables 5, 6, and 7). Similarly, Wolters *et al.* (2018) reported that the rhizosphere effect was stronger for young roots than for mature maize plants. In addition to the impacts of different stages of plant development, the long-term use of organic fertilizers such chicken manure and sewage sludge have been reported to have a major impact on microbial communities in the soil and the phyllosphere (Chen *et al.*, 2018). According to Correa-Galeote *et al.* (2018), another element that shapes maize endophytes is the history of soil cultivation, which increases the richness of bacterial communities over a prolonged period of soil cultivation as opposed to fallow soil. Both healthy and asymptomatic plants are colonized by a wide variety of microorganisms in nature (Roslan *et al.*, 2022). The intricate plant-associated microbial community is known as the second genome of plants because of its impact on plant growth and production (Hacquard, 2016). Notably, nutrient activation, stress tolerance, defense against soil-borne illnesses, and resilience to climate change-related environmental changes like drought, salt, and fluctuating temperatures are just a few of the ways the microbes help the host plants (Canarini *et al.*, 2019; Hassan *et al.*, 2019; Khan *et al.*, 2021; Lazcano *et al.*, 2021; Xiong *et al.*, 2021). This study found that the bacterial rhizosphere microbiome of okra showed a complex soil microbial community structure. This suggests that the rhizosphere soil microbial populations may be influenced by the various stages of plant development, which could be a crucial step in increasing maize and okra output and growth.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, field crops promoted bacterial, fungal and nematode population and diversity; there were variations in these microbial communities in response to plant growth and development. Measures of bacterial and fungal activity revealed that crop growth stage influences rhizodeposition. These communities response was obvious between seedling and matured crops and may reflect changes in the root exudates pattern of young crops to that of matured crops. It was observed in this study that Okra promoted the highest bacterial and fungal growth thus can be used as an intercrop to increase soil microbial biomass which aids in organic matter decomposition, thereby improving soil fertility.

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